

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D5.1 - First working actuation unit

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1 INTRODUCTION

The MAPWORMS project proposes a new robotic paradigm aimed at reproducing the shape-morphing capabilities of simplified forms of marine worms without implementing a central control strategy as in traditional machines, but by relying on synthetic soft actuation units integrated into a smart and modular architecture, and able to respond to different environmental stimuli (Figure 1).

Figure 1. (a) Body parts of Sipuncula worms which have been selected as main source of bioinspiration for the design of the final robot. (b) Design concept of the worm-inspired protruding robot that will be developed in the framework of the MAPWORMS project.

In this framework, Sipuncula (i.e., a class of unsegmented marine annelid worms) have been selected as the main source of bioinspiration for the design of the final robots due to the simple yet effective morphological structure of their bodies, able to allow for impressive deformations of their shape and protrusion abilities of part of their bodies. This class of worms can reach lengths up to three times their initial ones thanks to the protrusion of the introvert, which is the anterior part of their body, exploited for exploring the surrounding, burrowing, or getting food (Figure 1a).

The protrusion/ retraction mechanism of the introvert mainly relies on: (i) circular and longitudinal muscles working as an antagonistic pair in the elastic body wall; (ii) retractor muscles connecting the distal extremity of the introvert to the proximal part of the worm body (i.e., the trunk in which the introvert is folded in when not protruded, Figure 1a); (iii) the coelomic fluid contained in the coelomic cavity, thus creating the hydrostatic skeleton of the worm. In particular, the activation of the retractor muscles is mainly involved in pulling the introvert inside the trunk during the retraction mechanism. On the contrary, the circular muscles are the main actors in the protrusion mechanism of the introvert. Indeed, the protrusion mechanism is enabled by the action of circular muscles on the hydrostatic skeleton, which happens without volume changes of the coelomic fluid. When the circular muscles contract, the inner coelomic fluid is compressed, thus resulting in the eversion of the introvert. The longitudinal muscles have a less pronounced role in Sipuncula than in

regular Annelida. Indeed, in regular Annelida the contraction of longitudinal muscles shortens and thickens some body segments, allowing the chaetae to grip on the external surface. It happens while the contraction of the circular muscles squeezes and elongates other body segments, thus enabling the peristaltic movement of the worm. On the contrary, Sipuncula do not have a segmented body, and the peristaltic movements are very limited. Nevertheless, longitudinal muscles in Sipuncula allow for a differential thickening and stiffening of parts of the trunk and the introvert, thus playing an important role, for example, to get a grip on the sediment and to push the body forward or to get stuck into crevices, as well as during bending.

Taking inspiration from Sipuncula, the aim of the project is to design a new worm-inspired robot featured by a soft fluid-filled vesicle combined with different actuation units which mimic the general functions of the muscles, thus activating the fluidic transmission mechanisms described above for the biological counterpart. In particular, stimuli responsive materials and passive structural ones are combined to obtain actuation units able to respond to different environmental stimuli and with different motion capabilities. The stimuli-responsive materials allow for activating movements by relying on stiffness variations, chemical reactions and/or internal stresses occurring in response to environmental stimuli, such as light, pH, chemicals, or magnetic fields. Starting from basic contraction/ elongation behaviours of smart materials, very simple structures made of an active and passive layer and able to perform different primitives of movement can be obtained. For example, by tuning which direction the active layer contracts and/or extends, a rectangular shaped bilayer can bend, fold, or twist in several configurations as shown in Figure 2a. These bilayer structures can be combined in a smart architecture and integrated with fluid-filled vesicles, thus achieving more complex actuation units as shown in Figure 2b.

In this regard, shape-programmable magnetic materials have significant potential for achieving different motion primitives, especially at small scales. Indeed, even if the behaviour of shape-programmable magnetic materials is not based on material elongation or contraction as the examples reported in Figure 2a, they can allow for even more complex mechanical functionalities that are unattainable by different approaches. By including hard magnetic material particles (e.g., NdFeB) into a soft matrix (e.g., silicone), anisotropic magnetization programming can be accomplished, either during a 3D printing process or after molding. Through specific magnetization profile, these materials can reshape their geometries and achieve desired time-varying shapes by actuating magnetic fields.

In this framework, this Deliverable D5.1 - *First working actuation unit* reports the work carried out during the first 15 months of the project for the development of the actuation units to be used as building blocks of the final shape morphing robots. In particular, two different types of actuation units have been prototyped by exploiting different smart materials, i.e., magnetic responsive materials and smart hydrogels, able to respond to magnetic fields, and pH and temperature variations, respectively. At first, the simplest case study featured by bilayer bending structures have been considered for both actuation unit types. The

ability to react to the external stimuli with different intensities and to perform primitive bending movements were tested. In addition, the exploitation of a dedicated 3D printing setup suitable for soft materials was investigated for both solutions to allow for more complex designs through a simple manufacturing approach.

Figure 2. (a) Examples of motion primitives that can be achieved by exploiting bilayer structures. Starting from a simple architecture with an active (yellow) and passive (blue) layer materials, different primitives of motion can be achieved thanks to the responsiveness of the active one. (b) Examples of actuation units that can be achieved by combining a fluid-filled vesicle with the bilayer structures able to perform bending or twisting primitives of motion.

2 ACTUATION UNITS BASED ON MAGNETIC RESPONSIVE MATERIALS

2.1 BILAYER BENDING STRUCTURES

During the first 15 months of the project, bilayer structures consisting of a passive layer and an active one able to respond to external magnetic fields have been developed by SSSA to enable a first type of primitives of motion. In this case the bending motion is not produced by a contraction/expansion of the active layer, but by the interaction of specifically programmed magnetic domains in the active material with an external magnetic field. In particular, the developed bilayer structures can allow for different bending movements

depending on their configuration, i.e., whether the active or passive layer is facing an external permanent magnet (EPM) and depending on the direction and intensity of the external magnetic field (Figure 3). In future, the bilayer structures can be accordingly shaped and imparted with a different magnetization profile to produce different primitive movements as the one reported in Figure 2a.

Figure 3. An example actuation unit based on magnetic responsive material showing its response under different actuation conditions.

For the manufacturing, an Automatic Film Applicator Standard (model AB3652, TQC Sheen, Industrial Physics) was used to improve the accuracy and reproducibility of the process. Indeed, it allows for more uniform layers with reproducible thickness, avoiding possible variations caused by human factors. At first, a layer of a magnetic soft composite made of silicone Ecoflex 0010 (Shore A; Smooth-On, Inc.) and Neodymium Iron Boron (NdFeB) magnetic particles (5 μm) was deposited by setting the desired thickness. When this active layer was partially cured, a layer of passive material made of pure silicone Ecoflex 0010 of the required thickness was deposited over it and the bilayer was left to be fully cured. Two different layer thickness values were considered: 0.5 mm and 1 mm. Then, the desired rectangular shapes with sizes equal to 1 cm x 3 cm were cut from the bilayer using template routing. In future, a laser cutter could be used for further improving the manufacturing process and for allowing more complex shapes.

Since the presence of a passive layer influences the final bending capabilities, also a control sample of active layer was fabricated for comparison. To generate motion capabilities in the bilayer as seen in the first motion primitives in Figure 2a, it is necessary to magnetize the magnetic layer so that the desired magnetic anisotropic profile can be imparted to it. Thus, the manufactured bilayer structures were folded along their length and a strong magnetic field (2 T) was applied along the length through an impulse magnetizer to allow for bending

motion. This resulted in the bilayer being divided into two halves, each one having a magnetization opposite to the other as shown in Figure 3. Thus, when an external field was applied, the two halves of the bilayer aligned their magnetization with the external field and the bending motion was accomplished as in Figure 3 (right). If the external field was along the +Z axis, the bilayer assumed a U shape, while when the external field is along the -Z axis, the bilayer took a \cap shape.

The motion capabilities of the bilayer were characterized by measuring the bending angle when actuated using an EPM. The direction (+Z, -Z) and magnitude (10 mT, 30 mT, 50 mT) of the applied magnetic field at the bilayer in rest state were varied (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**) along with the configuration of the bilayer, i.e., whether the active or passive layer was facing the EPM or not. In order to obtain different magnetic field values acting on the bilayer, the distance r (Figure 4) between the EPM and the surface on which the bilayer was attached, was changed.

A simplified mathematical model, namely the dipole model, was used to calculate the distance required to produce the three desired magnetic field values (10 mT, 30 mT, 50 mT). The magnetic field strength generated by the EPM at a given distance r can then be calculated using the following formula:

$$B(r) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \left(\frac{3r(m \cdot r)}{r^5} - \frac{m}{r^3} \right)$$

Where μ_0 is the vacuum permeability constant, and m the magnetic moment.

From this expression, it is possible to calculate the distance r required to impose an accurate value of the desired magnetic field (10 mT, 30 mT, 50 mT):

$$r = \sqrt[3]{\frac{\mu_0 m}{2\pi B}}$$

Thus resulting in r equal to 15.0 cm, 10.4 cm, and 8.8 cm (Table 1). A magnetic sensor (3D Magnetic Sensor 2GO, Infineon, Germany) was used to verify the magnetic field at these distances (Table 1).

Table 1. Relation between the distance of the EPM from the bilayer and the magnitude of magnetic field at the bilayer.

Desired magnetic field	Distance from the magnet (r)	Measured magnetic field
10 mT	15.0 cm	10.18 ± 0.07 mT
30 mT	10.4 cm	30.47 ± 0.45 mT
50 mT	8.8 cm	50.11 ± 0.29 mT

The bending angle of the bilayer was recorded 5 times for 5 different samples. In particular, images of the curved bilayer were acquired for each test conditions, and the skeleton of the bilayer was extracted using MATLAB. The bending angle was then calculated as the angle formed by the extremities of the bilayer at its centre point (Figure 4). It was calculated using this formula:

$$\alpha = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{v_1 \cdot v_2}{\|v_1\| * \|v_2\|} \right)$$

Thus, it has to be noted that a smaller bending angle corresponded to a higher curvature of the bilayer.

Figure 4. (A) Bending characterization setup. Controlling the distance (r) between the external permanent magnet and the bilayer, the magnitude and direction of the magnetic field was controlled. (B-C) When actuated, images of the bilayer are taken from which its skeleton is extracted.

The resulting maximum bending angle values for 50 mT fields are given in the Table 2. In particular, it was found that the bending angle in the U configuration was higher than in the \cap configuration, for all three values of the magnetic field (i.e., the bilayer structure was more bent in the \cap configuration with respect to the U configuration for the same distance). Indeed, the bending in the bilayer was induced due to the two halves of it interacting with the external magnetic field. Therefore, any variation in the strength of the field at extremities affected the final results.

The magnetic torque τ on a body of magnetization m at an angle θ with and in a field of strength B and its magnitude are given by the following equation, respectively:

$$\tau = m \times B$$

$$|\tau| = |m| |B| \sin(\theta)$$

Figure 5A shows the relationship between the magnetic field strength at the centre point of the bilayer in rest state as a function of its distance from the centre of the permanent magnet. Figure 5B-C show the magnetic field direction and strength when the field at the centre point of the bilayer structure is 50 mT. When the bilayer bends in a U shape, the extremities move to regions of lower magnetic fields which means $|B|$ gets reduced. The direction of the field (represented by brown arrows in Figure 5B-C) at each extremity is also

not vertical anymore and it creates with the direction of the magnetization at the bilayer extremity (represented by red arrows in Figure 5B-C) a θ angle (the angle between red and brown arrows at the extremities in Figure 5B-C) close to 0° . Both these factors negatively affect the torque acting on the bilayer. On the other hand, when the bilayer bends in a \cap shape, the drop in the field strength ($|B|$) at extremities is not so severe (Figure 5C). The direction of the field at each extremity in this case too is not vertical but creates a θ angle much greater than $>0^\circ$ with the magnetization direction of the extremities. Therefore, the bilayer experiences a greater torque when bending in a \cap shape as compared to when bending in a U shape. This results in slightly greater bending in the \cap configuration (Table 1).

Figure 5. Magnetic field representation. (A) The relationship between the magnetic field strength with the distance from the permanent magnet. **(B-C)** The direction of brown arrows represents the direction of the magnetic field at that point. The length of the brown arrows represents the relative strength of the magnetic field with respect to each other. The red arrows represent the direction of magnetization of the extremities. **(B)** When the field is applied in +Z direction, the bilayer bends in a U shape and **(C)** when the field is applied in -Z direction, the bilayer instead bends in a \cap shape.

Table 2 Smallest bending angle values for different actuation configurations.

Layer thickness	Sample	U configuration	\cap configuration
0.5 mm	Control	19.4°	15.8°
	Bilayer	38.8°	20.8°
1 mm	Control	33.0°	17.3°
	Bilayer	47.2°	34.3°

As expected, the control samples bent more than the bilayer structures. Indeed, in the control samples, the resistance forces of the compressed passive layer or the elastic forces due to the elongated passive layer were not present. However, the final aim is to integrate the active layers on passive soft fluid-filled vesicles in order to mimic the fluidic transmission mechanisms of the worms (Figure 2b). Thus, the reported bilayer bending actuation units have to be considered the first step in the achievement of the final actuation units of the

worm-inspired robot. Indeed, more complex motion capabilities can be enabled by the combination of the primitive bending motions into a smart architecture. In this regard, two examples are shown in Figure 6. In the future months, these actuation units will be exploited to compress a liquid-filled inner body, thus resulting in designs as the ones shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 6. Example of actuation units developed by combining different bilayer bending structures. (A) Four bilayer units are combined together in a cross structure. Each bilayer has a magnetization profile as schematized at the top. (B) Four bilayer units are held together by two rigid passive bases at two ends of the cuboid (schematized in blue). Each bilayer has a magnetization profile as shown in the schematic at the top.

2.2 3D PRINTING

For the development of complex magnetic actuation units, a 3D printer could be used which gives us the freedom to choose different materials, shapes, and sizes of the printed structure. These advantages combined with the benefits provided by magnetic anisotropy can lead to rapid prototyping of smart complex actuation units. In this framework, a 3D printing set up that allows for programmable magnetization was developed by the lead beneficiary of this deliverable (SSSA) in the recent past and is available to be used in the MAPWORMS project for the development of complex magnetic actuation units [1].

The developed methodology works with a magnetic composite of Neodymium Iron Boron (NdFeB) particles ($5\mu\text{m}$) uniformly dispersed in a high viscosity Ultra-violet (UV) curable resin. NdFeB is chosen due to its high remanence which imparts high magnetization to the printed structure while helping with magnetic anisotropy. High viscosity UV-curable resin was chosen to prevent magnetic particles from agglomerating while allowing its extrusion through narrow nozzles. The composite is then magnetised in a high intensity magnetic field (2T). This magnetization step helps the magnetic composite in retaining its shape after extrusion during curing. The composite is then extruded through the nozzle of a 3D biplotter (Omega,

3Dynamic) which has three mutually orthogonal electromagnetic (EM) coils placed symmetrically around it such that the nozzle is at the same angle of 54.74° from every coil. During extrusion of the ink, the coil system produces magnetic fields which align the magnetic particles in the ink in the desired directions. After extrusion, a high intensity UV light is used to cure the printed material which locks the shape of the structure and the orientation of the particles within it (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Schematization of the custom 3D printing methodology capable of fabricating soft structures with programmable magnetization.

Starting from these previous results, SSSA is now working on defining the most suitable 3D printing parameters that can be set for different soft materials and for the achievement of more complex architecture.

3 ACTUATION UNITS BASED ON SMART HYDROGELS

3.1 BILAYER BENDING STRUCTURES

A second type of actuations units are based on smart hydrogels able to respond to pH and temperature variations (Figure 8). As reported in the Deliverable D4.1 - *Delivery of available smart responsive hydrogels for preliminary modelling and for devising integration possibilities*, HUJI has developed stiffness-switchable pH-responsive DNA based hydrogels and cryogels. By subjecting the hydrogel/cryogel to pH=7.4 and pH=5.5, the hydrogel/cryogel was cycled between high and low stiffness states (the hydrogel has low stiffness at pH 5.5 and higher stiffness at pH 7.4). At the same time, bilayer matrices consisting of a thermoresponsive poly-N-isopropylacrylamide (pNIPAM) gel layer and a pH-sensitive polyacrylamide (pAAM) layer which can bend in response to either temperature changes or pH changes have been

developed. The mechanical, stiffness-controlled bending are depicted in Figure 8. Bilayer constructs consisting of pNIPAM (cryogel)/pAAm (cryogel) and pNIPAM (cryogel)/pAAm (hydrogel/cryogel) were manufactured by moulding technique and the dynamics of the bending of the device were examined under auxiliary pH-triggering. The reversibility of the mechanical bending functions of the different bilayer devices were demonstrated (see Deliverable D4.1 - *Delivery of available smart responsive hydrogels for preliminary modelling and for devising integration possibilities*).

Figure 8. Integration of pH and temperature responsive hydrogels to produce actuation units capable of being actuated by multiple stimuli.

3.2 3D PRINTING

SSSA has been working on the development of the 3D printing set-up suitable for this smart hydrogels. In particular, the most efficient parameters that have to be selected for the 3D printing process are under investigation with the 3D printer Omega - 3Dynamic, the same exploited for the magnetic responsive materials. In this regard, the metal-ion-crosslinked CarboxyMethylCellulose (CMC) hydrogel is used as alternative material to DNA-based hydrogels since the latter are highly technical, cost-intensive, and sensitive materials and CMC shows mechanical properties and viscosity comparable to DNA-based hydrogels exploited by HUJI for the bilayer structures [2, 3].

In this regard, a partial crosslinking of the CMC polymer solution was considered for printing at first. However, when the CMC was dispersed in the crosslinker, it made lumps and an

inhomogeneous and unprintable hydrogel was obtained (Figure 9). Therefore, the development shifted to printing the CMC polymer and the crosslinker separately.

Figure 9. 3D printing preliminary result. (A) Partially crosslinked CMC hydrogel forming lumps making it unsuitable for printing. (B) CMC straight line printed using a 0.45 mm needle.

It was found that the 3D printing of the CMC polymer was highly variable probably due to non-constant environmental conditions such as temperature and humidity and due to the very low viscosity of the hydrogels. To avoid this, CMC polymer was printed directly into the crosslinker bath (Iron Chloride: FeCl_3), but the hurdle of inconsistency still persisted (Figure 10). Indeed, inhomogeneous polymerization of the 3D printed CMC was found.

Figure 10. Attempted printing of the CMC polymer solution in the crosslinker bath.

Nonetheless, a few successful attempts of printing CMC polymer into a rectangular layer were achieved after which the crosslinker was manually added to form the hydrogel layer (Figure 11). Due to the very low viscosity of the hydrogels, a controlled printing could not yet be achieved for more complex designs than a single layer. Therefore, SSSA is looking at the state of the art to find a solution to this hurdle. If no practical solutions will be found, alternative fabrication techniques will be exploited (e.g., moulding).

Figure 11. CMC hydrogel: CMC polymer solution crosslinked by adding FeCl_3 crosslinker manually.

CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable deals with using three stimuli – magnetic fields, pH, and temperature - for the development of the actuation units to be used as building blocks of the final shape-morphing robot. Magnetic fields are highly controllable, safe to interact with living tissue, and offers remote actuation abilities, making them highly suitable for medical applications. On the other hand, different regions in the body have different pH. Therefore, pH can be used as an endogenous stimulus in applications targeting specific parts of the body. The combination of these different actuation technologies, together with a temperature variation mediated by the magnetic particles embedded in the magnetic unit, has then the potential to enlarge the capabilities of the final robot in executing different tasks, in the medical as well as in other possible application scenarios.

Through moulding and template routing, magnetic bilayer actuation unit was fabricated able to bend in the presence of an external magnetic field. Different configurations of the bilayer were characterised in terms of their bending angle and compared with the bending of the control samples. The bending was also characterized by varying the direction and magnitude of the applied magnetic field. For more complex actuation units, a novel 3D printing technology is under investigation.

HUJI has developed pH and temperature responsive hydrogels and developed bilayer bending structures. In this regard, SSSA is working on the 3D printing of materials with similar mechanical properties and viscosities to allow for more complex actuation units. However, results have not been fully successful so far and possible solutions are under analysis.

The reported results represent the first steps in the design of the multilayered structures with primitive motion capabilities used to create the actuation units to be integrated with the passive fluid-filled vesicle in the final robot (Figure 2). In this regard, future works will be focused on the combination of these simple structures to enable more complex motion capabilities. Efforts will also continue to be made on the integration of the actuation units with soft passive fluid-filled chambers in order to achieve the fluidic transmission mechanisms presented by the biological counterpart and fundamental in the shape-morphing strategy.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. H. D. Ansari et al., "3D Printing of Small-Scale Soft Robots with Programmable Magnetization," vol. 33, no. 15, p. 2211918, 2023.
- [2] M. Fadeev et al., "Redox-triggered hydrogels revealing switchable stiffness properties and shape-memory functions," *Polymer Chemistry*, 10.1039/C8PY00515J vol. 9, no. 21, pp. 2905-2912, 2018.
- [3] I. Willner and G. Davidson-Rozenfeld, "MAPWORMS Deliverable 4.1."